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THE MENINGO-ORBITAL FORAMEN ON MALE AND FEMALE SKULLS IN THE AGE ASPECT

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Abstract

The aim of the investigation was to study the meningo-orbital foramina on male and female skulls in terms of age. The material for the study was 40 male and 64 female skulls belonging to the adolescence (1st age period), I (2nd age period), and II (3rd age period) stages of adulthood, as well as the elderly age period (4th age period). Of the 40 male skulls we studied, the meningo-orbital foramen was found on 15 of them (37.5%); at the same time, on 12 of the skulls with the meningo-orbital foramen, it was detected unilaterally (30%) and on three bilaterally (7.5%). As can be seen from the table, on male skulls with the unilateral presence of the meningo-orbital foramen, the number of these foramina did not exceed 1. The meningo-orbital foramina were found in all age periods studied on male skulls. At the same time, they were always present on the left side but absent on the right side in the 1st and 3rd age periods. Despite this, the number of right meningo-orbital foramina was greater than that of the left ones. More often, meningo-orbital foramina were found on the right male orbits in the 2nd age period. The bilateral meningo-orbital foramina on male skulls were found only in the 2nd age period. Of the 64 female skulls examined, 31 had the meningo-orbital foramina (48.4%). On 18 female skulls, the meningo-orbital foramen was found unilaterally (28.1%) and on 13 bilaterally (20.3%). Two meningo-orbital foramina were found on one right orbit of the 1st and on one right orbit of the 2nd age periods. On female skulls with bilateral occurrences of the meningo-orbital foramina, variant A was predominant. This variant was found on 3 skulls of the 2nd age period (4.7%), on 3 skulls of the 3rd age period (4.7%), and also on 2 4th age period skulls (3.1%). Variant B was investigated in all studied age groups of female skulls (one skull in each group). Variant D was found on one female skull belonging to the 4th age period.

Keywords: meningo-orbital foramen, skull, orbit, age periods.

Introduction. The study of the meningo-orbital foramen is of great value primarily from a clinical point of view, and it has applied importance in neurosurgery, ophthalmology, and plastic and reconstructive surgery. A review of the literature showed that interest in the meningo-orbital foramen has increased. This rising interest can be explained by the demands of clinical medicine. The meningo-orbital foramen is a small opening in the orbit, lateral to the lateral end of the superior orbital fissure. It is widely known that the meningo-orbital foramen contains the orbital branch of the middle meningeal artery. The foramina can be single or multiple and located in the posterior superior part of the lateral wall of the orbit or in the posterolateral part of the

roof of the orbit. The meningo-orbital foramen is an additional communication link between the orbit and the cranial cavity. This bony canal, not always present in the human skull, contains a branch from the middle meningeal artery, providing accessory blood supply to the orbit and its contents. This vessel, like the meningo-orbital foramen itself, shows a great degree of variation [1, p. 323-5; 2, p. 880-5].

In the presence of a meningo-orbital foramen, it forms an extra connection between the orbit and the middle cranial fossa. Its content is an arterial anastomosis between the middle meningeal artery, the meningo-lacrimal branch, and the lacrimal artery, the meningeal branch [3, p. 517-9]. The literature also indicates that

the meningo-orbital foramen connects the orbit and anterior cranial fossa [4, p. 268-70]. Other names for this foramen are also used, namely: cranio-orbital foramen, lacrimal foramen, foramen of Hyrtl, foramen meningo-orbitale, sinus canal foramen, and sphenofrontal foramen [3, p. 517-9; 5, p.2297-300].

During operations in the cavity of the orbit, the meningo-orbital foramen is often located near the operation zone, and its precise localization helps to avoid unexpected bleeding during the intervention [6, p. 1033-7; 7, p. 729-31]. It should be noted that the exact location of each meningo-orbital foramen was rarely the same between the skulls or on different sides of the same skull. However, the meningo-orbital foramen was invariably found near the suture line of the greater wing of the sphenoid bone, leading to the superior orbital fissure [8, p. 119-25].

According to [9, p. 957-64] in all preparations, the lacrimal artery arises from the ophthalmic artery. Recurrent meningeal branch was found in six cases on the right and in five cases on the left. On the right, in two cases out of six, the recurrent meningeal branch passed through the meningo-orbital foramen; in the remaining four cases, this branch, having passed through the superior orbital fissure, emptied into the middle cranial fossa. On the left of the five cases, in two, the recurrent meningeal branch passed through the meningo-orbital foramen; in the remaining three, the passage of the indicated branch through the superior orbital fissure into the middle cranial fossa was again found.

[2, p. 880-5] indicates that a total of 16 meningo-orbital foramina were found through which a thin probe could be passed. Fourteen of them merge into canals that empty posteriorly into the bone and open into the middle cranial fossa at the lateral end of the superior orbital fissure. The other two of these foramina communicated with the anterior cranial fossa, and both were connected with a more posterior foramen that communicated with the middle cranial fossa.

The meningo-orbital foramen was present in three of the most common places: (1) above the suture between the orbital plate of the frontal bone and the greater wing sphenoid (epi-sutural), (ii) in the suture (sutural), and (iii) below the suture in the greater wing sphenoid (hyposutural) [10, p. 52-5].

However, it is noted that there is a lack of clarity in the literature regarding the morphology and morphometry of the meningo-orbital foramen [6, p.1033-7]. Particularly noteworthy is the somewhat scarce information on the peculiarities of the incidence of the

meningo-orbital foramina in male and female skulls. Also, even more scarce data are found in the study of the meningo-orbital foramina on male and female skulls in the age aspect. Given that the orbits located in the upper part of the facial skeleton show a high severity of morphological features in terms of age and gender [11, p.29-34], the study of the meningo-orbital foramina in these aspects becomes relevant.

The aim of the investigation was to study the meningo-orbital foramina on male and female skulls in terms of age.

Materials and research methods. The material for the study was 40 male and 64 female skulls belonging to the adolescence (1st age period), I (2nd age period), and II (3rd age period) stages of adulthood, as well as the elderly age period (4th age period). Of the studied skulls, 13 belonged to the 1st age period (5 males, 8 females), 42 skulls (16 males, 26 females) belonged to the 2nd age period, and 33 skulls (12 males, 21 females) belonged to the 3rd age period. 16 skulls (7 males and 9 females) made up the 4th age period. In the case of the presence of a foramen on the side of the orbit, the patency of this foramen was detected using a thin wire (fig.1). After fixing the wire on the orbit, the other end of the wire was studied by intracranial endoscopy in order to study the connection between the orbit and the cranial cavity. The study also used the cranioscopic method and computed tomography.

Results. The results of the study are shown in Table 1.

The meningo-orbital foramen in the skulls we studied was found both on one (left or right) and simultaneously on both orbits. Of the 40 male skulls we studied, the meningo-orbital foramen was found on 15 of them (37.5%); at the same time, on 12 of the skulls with the meningo-orbital foramen, it was detected unilaterally (30%) and on three bilaterally (7.5%). As can be seen from the table, on male skulls with the unilateral presence of the meningo-orbital foramen, the number of these foramina did not exceed 1.

The meningo-orbital foramina were found in all age periods studied on male skulls. At the same time, they were always present on the left side but absent on the right side in the 1st and 3rd age periods. Despite this, the number of right meningo-orbital foramina was greater than that of the left ones. More often, meningo-orbital foramina were found on the right male orbits in the 2nd age period.

Table 1.

Frequency of the meningo-orbital foramen on male and female skulls.

Age periods	Male								Female							
	Left		Right		Bilateral				Left		Right		Bilateral			
	1	2	1	2	1:1	2:1	1:2	2:2	1	2	1	2	1:1	2:1	1:2	2:2
	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D
1 st age period	1										1	1		1		
2 nd age period	1		4		2		1		6		3	1	3	1		
3 rd age period	2								4		1		3	1		
4 th age period	1		3								1		2	1		1
Total number of cases	5		7		2		1		10		6	2	8	4		1
Total number of foramina	5		7		4		3		10		6	4	16	12		2

The bilateral meningo-orbital foramina were found in the following variants: one foramen in each orbit (variant A); two foramina in the left orbit and one foramen in the right orbit (variant B); one foramen in the left orbit with two meningo-orbital foramina in the right orbit (variant C); and finally, two meningo-orbital foramina in both orbits (variant D). The bilateral meningo-orbital foramina on male skulls were found only in the 2nd age period. Variant A was found on two male skulls (5%); variant C (2.5%) was examined on one skull. Variants B and D on male skulls have not been identified.

Fig. 1. The metallic wire in the meningo-orbital foramen. Intracranial endoscopy.

Of the 64 female skulls examined, 31 had the meningo-orbital foramina (48.4%). On 18 female skulls, the meningo-orbital foramen was found unilaterally (28.1%) and on 13 bilaterally (20.3%). In contrast to male skulls, the incidence of the meningo-orbital foramina in female orbits was higher on the left side. Despite such frequent detection, the meningo-orbital foramina were not found on the left orbits in the 1st and 4th age periods. On the female orbits on the right side, the investigated foramen was found in all age periods. Also, two meningo-orbital foramina were found on one right orbit of the 1st and on one right orbit of the 2nd age periods.

On female skulls with bilateral occurrences of the meningo-orbital foramina, variant A was predominant.

This variant was found on 3 skulls of the 2nd age period (4.7%), on 3 skulls of the 3rd age period (4.7%), and also on 2 4th age period skulls (3.1%). Variant B was investigated in all studied age groups of female skulls (one skull in each group) (fig.2). Variant C was not found in female skulls. Variant D was found on one female skull belonging to the 4th age period.

In general, on the studied 104 male and female skulls (in other words, on 208 orbits), the meningo-orbital foramina were found in 44.2%. From the studied material, it follows that the meningo-orbital foramina were found unilaterally in 28.8% of cases and bilaterally in 15.4% of cases.

Fig.2. CT scan. Female skull, 2nd age period: two foramina on the left, one foramen on the right. The foramina are indicated by arrows. On the reconstruction of the skull, the foramina are indicated by numbers.

Discussion. As noted, interest in the meningo-orbital foramina is dictated, first of all, by the needs of clinical medicine. The success of developing neurosurgery and ophthalmology depends on accurate and detailed anatomical data in the surgical field. In this aspect, of particular interest are those structures, the identification of which, although not permanent, and the presence of which during surgical intervention can lead to complications and sometimes to death. In the study we have undertaken, we have tried to touch upon the incidence of the meningo-orbital foramina in the most detailed age and gender aspects.

According to [1, p. 323-5] 92 orbits were studied on 46 macerated human skulls (25 male and 21 female). Although the incidence of meningo-orbital foramen was 28% in the material as a whole, it was 40.5% for female skulls compared to 18% for male skulls. This difference was statistically significant. Double foramen occurred in three orbits, and triple foramen were found in one orbit. This means that, in general, multiple foramen in the material were observed in 4% of cases. In our opinion, if the study covered more skulls, we could count on a higher percentage of meningo-orbital foramen detection.

There has also been an increased interest in the study of the meningo-orbital foramen from an anthropological aspect. In the study of 138 South Indian adult skulls, the meningo-orbital foramen was present in 80.4% of the population, according to [3, p. 517-9]. The high frequency of the meningo-orbital foramen is found in the study [10, p. 52-5]. According to this work, the foramen meningo-orbitale was found in 145 (66%) skulls and absent in 75 (34%) skulls. It was present unilaterally in 107 (74%) and bilaterally in 38 (26%) cases.

Our results are consistent with the data of [12, p. 43-44], according to which foramen meningo-orbitale was found in 43 skulls (44.32%) of the total number of 97 skulls studied. It was unilateral (either right or left) in 27 skulls (27.83%) and bilateral in 16 skulls (16.49%). It turned out that it is double in 6 orbits (3.09%): 4 on the right and 2 on the left.

Out of 150 intact orbits of adults, cribra orbitalia were found in 35 (23.3%). Examination of these 35 orbits with cribra orbitalia showed that 32 (91.4%) of them had a meningo-orbital foramen. In the absence of a meningo-orbital foramen, cribra orbitalia were found only in three cases (3:150; 2.0%). Fisher's exact test showed that cribra orbitalia and meningo-orbital foramen are statistically dependent variables. This study shows that the meningo-orbital foramen indicates an anatomical predisposition to cribra orbitalia. Conversely, the occurrence of cribra orbitalia is unlikely in the absence of a meningo-orbital foramen [13, p.1629-1671].

The study [5, p.2297-300] indicates that out of 200 orbits, the cranio-orbital foramen was observed in 40 skulls (57 orbits). In 23 skulls, the foramen was unilateral. In 17 skulls (34 orbits), this foramen was bilateral. One skull had a single foramen on the right orbit and a double foramen on the left orbit. It should be noted that the study used craniological material of unknown sex.

According to [4, p. 268-70], the meningo-orbital foramen existed in thirty-two orbits (18 right, 14 left) out of the hundred orbits studied.

Thus, despite a sufficient number of studies on the meningo-orbital foramen, generalizing works that reveal such important aspects as gender and age have not been carried out. We found that on the studied 104 male and female skulls, the meningo-orbital foramina were found in 44.2%. From the studied material, it follows that the meningo-orbital foramina were found unilaterally in 28.8% of cases and bilaterally in 15.4% of cases. In our opinion, noteworthy is the absence of some variants of the occurrence of bilateral meningo-orbital foramina (namely, variants B and D on male skulls and variant C on female skulls). Increasing the number of skulls examined will perhaps bring out some of these variants. In addition, the use of computed tomography by us will help in radiological studies for optimal visualization of the meningo-orbital foramen. The method of intracranial endoscopy, also used by us for the first time to identify the meningo-orbital foramen, made it possible to clearly determine the patency and destination of these foramina.

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PROSTHETICS WITH REMOVABLE PROSTHESES IN PATIENTS WITH EDEMA OF THE MUCOUS MEMBRANE OF THE PROSTHETIC FIELD

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Abstract

Recently, there has been an increase in the number of patients with a complete absence of teeth and complaints of deterioration in the stabilization of complete removable dentures during the day. The main reason for unsatisfactory fixation of prostheses is periodic swelling of the oral mucosa due to impaired kidney function and pathology of the cardiovascular system. In this regard, it is necessary to obtain impressions taking into account the degree of edema of the mucous membrane of the prosthetic bed, which will improve the functional characteristics and stabilization of complete removable dentures, reduce the number of corrections and significantly reduce the adaptation period.

Keywords: complete secondary adentia, edema of the oral mucosa, prosthetics.

The problem of complete loss of teeth and prosthetics with removable dentures remains relevant today. In the general structure of the population in need of removable prosthetics, persons with a complete absence of teeth make up about 35–40% [1,2, 3], and the need for the manufacture of complete removable dentures tends to increase. According to WHO, for various reasons, up to 26 % of patients with complete loss of teeth cannot use the manufactured plate prostheses due to their unsatisfactory fixation [4, 5,6], which leads to a decrease in social activity of people and a deterioration in their quality of life [6]. This is due to a number of factors, among which an important role is played by the oral mucosa [7]. The use of implants for prosthetics is quite expensive and is not always shown, which makes them unaffordable for most patients. In the last 10 years, the number of patients with complaints about changes in the stabilization of complete removable dentures during the day has increased: it worsens in the morning or after lunch. At the same time, some patients complain of a “tight” prosthesis in the morning or in the afternoon, which then becomes “wide” and is poorly fixed. All these complaints increase the number of corrections of the manufactured prostheses, as a result of which their stabilization worsens, which leads to serious violations of the adaptation process. Often, patients

continue to use old prostheses, not because of their aesthetic and functional shortcomings [8]. The current methods of re-prosthetics in severe jaw atrophy are primarily aimed at creating maximum comfort from the use of complete removable dentures [9, 10]. In our opinion, today they do not pay due attention to the study of the frequency of unsatisfactory fixation of complete removable dentures in patients with somatic diseases who have different degrees of swelling of the oral mucosa and they change during the day.

The aim of the study is to improve the quality of fixation of prostheses in patients with complete loss of teeth and periodic edema of the oral mucosa caused by chronic renal failure of cardiac origin, by rationalizing the method of obtaining functional impressions for the manufacture of complete removable dentures.

Material and research methods

To achieve the goals and objectives set in the work, 30 patients aged 55 to 70 years who had mucosal edema and complained of poor fixation of complete removable dentures during the day were examined. In this regard, there was a need for additional examination of such patients with an in-depth study of concomitant diseases [11] and the state of the mucosa.

To establish the time interval in which the oral mucosa had an "average" degree of edema, old or tempo-